

Modular programme for Education and Training
EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATOR

M#5 Hands-on Teaching

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TECHNICAL SHEET

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For further information on the EduPASS Project please follow the link:

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Six Core Modules of EduPASS for Early Childhood Educators

The following are the proposed six core modules for Early Childhood Educators education and training programmes that were developed as part of the EduPASS Erasmus+ Project. The core modules should be seen as a flexible reference point which require contextual adaptation. Those individuals and/or organisations using the six core modules to develop learning opportunities for Early Childhood Educators should use the knowledge of their specific context to customise the modules to fit their needs, resources and objectives.

Each of the six EduPASS core modules proposed for ECE education and training programmes was developed building on the knowledge and insights, which can be found in the [European Quality Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care \(ECEC\)](#). The ECEC describes the most important the proposal for key principles of a [Quality Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care \(2014\)](#).

The respective module number and order in which the modules are presented in the table below do not indicate that modules must be introduced in this specific order, when implementing an Early Childhood Educator education and training programme. Rather the numbers simply serve as distinct denominators to help identify specific modules in the overall context of the EduPASS ECE education and training programme.

Core Module Overview

No	Module Title	Description
1	Daily Physical Activity and Play	<p>The module teaches the theoretical basis of the concept of holistic development of children, focusing on changes experienced by children aged 3 to 6 years.</p> <p>It emphasizes the importance of physical activity and play in children's overall development and well-being and highlights the benefits of physical activity during childhood, as well as the potential risks of inactivity on overall health. Additionally, recommendations for children's physical activity levels, strategies for implementation, and the development of skills for assessing the recommended daily physical activity level for children are provided.</p> <p>Finally, a theoretical background for developing intervention programs aimed at improving children's daily physical activity levels is presented. It includes practical workshops and the development of skills for designing and implementing programs to enhance children's daily physical activity levels.</p>

2	Principles of Educating Children	<p>This module aims to guarantee the comprehensive development of children through physical education. For this, different learning units, based mainly on the game, will be carried out such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • motor stories • music, dance and movement • energetic games • games with balls • activities that involve balance, development of laterality, coordination and body awareness • manipulative and construction games
3	Inclusive Teaching	<p>The module aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introduce the theoretical foundations of the concept of inclusion. This includes the legal background (e.g., UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities and national legislation), the requirements and goals of inclusion, and didactic models, principles, methods, and strategies for inclusive teaching. • provide opportunities to practically apply and reflect about the principles, methods, and resources of inclusive teaching using specific teaching/case scenarios.
4	Fundamental Movement Skills, Play and Motor Skill Assessment	<p>The module aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • introduce the theoretical basics of the concept of fundamental movement skills and play and their importance for children. This includes the structure of fundamental movement skills, their role in children’s development, and didactic principles and methods to promote fundamental movement skills and play. • provide guidance on the practical use of the principles, methods, and resources of teaching/promoting fundamental movement skills and play. • introduce both the theoretical knowledge and the practical skills to objectively measure fundamental movement skills of children using motor tests
5	Hands-on Teaching	<p>This module is designed to enhance the practical skills of Early Childhood Educators through direct participation in learning activities. Through a hands-on approach, participants will develop key skills to foster high-quality interactions with children and create an inclusive learning environment.</p> <p>During the module, Early Childhood Educators will engage in interactive exercises and receive immediate feedback, allowing them to directly apply the pedagogical techniques learned to their educational settings. Strategies for observation and documentation, group dynamics management, and conflict resolution will be addressed, all focused on adapting pedagogical practices to the individual and collective needs of children.</p>

6	Plan, Reflect and Learn	<p>The application of teaching skills, observation and effective decision making is essential to fulfil teaching PAMPS for early childhood and is a cross-cutting capability that should be developed in all ECEs at each stage of their development. The ECE plans, evaluates and reflects each practice and event seeking improvements. In addition, this personal evaluation and reflection underpin a process of ongoing learning and professional development. An important element of this process is the ECE's efforts to with other ECEs in the process.</p> <p>Reflection plays a vital role in early childhood settings. It provides continuous professional development, support, and feedback for all members involved and gives ECEs a safe space to discuss challenging experiences and related feelings. It lays the groundwork for ongoing professional development through consistent self-reflection, community support, and emotional awareness. It's critical that educators can manage the feelings that come with stress to support children's development, communicate effectively with co-workers and families, and find job satisfaction.</p> <p>Questioning what learning and development is taking place to make meaning of what has been observed is crucial for ECE. ECE students should be able to describe why the events are significant to the child and to describe why this experience was important for the child involved.</p>
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Core Module Structure

Core Module	Hands-on Teaching
Module Number	5
Core Module Aim	<p>The aim of the core module is to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhance the practical skills of Early Childhood Educators through direct participation in learning activities, promoting quality interactions and an inclusive learning environment.
Module Description	<p>This module is designed to enhance the practical skills of Early Childhood Educators through direct participation in learning activities. Through a hands-on approach, participants will develop key skills to foster high-quality interactions with children and create an inclusive learning environment.</p> <p>During the module, Early Childhood Educators will engage in interactive exercises and receive immediate feedback, allowing them to directly apply the pedagogical techniques learned to their educational settings. Strategies for observation and documentation, group dynamics management, and conflict resolution will be addressed, all focused on adapting pedagogical practices to the individual and collective needs of children.</p>
Module Duration	30 hours
Facilities and Equipment	A flexible classroom, practice room, gym, audiovisual technology, educational materials, and internet access
Methodology	Methodology includes interactive practical activities, immediate feedback, simulations in real environments, observation and documentation, group dynamics management, and conflict resolution, fostering the adaptation of pedagogical practices to the individual and collective needs of children, specifically aimed at early childhood education professionals.
Coaching Materials	Didactic materials, audiovisual technology, educational toys, manuals, mobile whiteboards, and internet access for early childhood educators.
Suggested Readings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dietze, B., & Kashin, D. (2018). <i>Playing and learning in early childhood education</i>. Pearson Canada. Link: https://www.pearson.com/en-ca/subject-catalog/p/playing-and-learning-in-early-childhood-education/P200000010198/9780137674244 Fellowes, J., & Oakley, G. (2011). <i>Language, literacy and early childhood education</i>. Oxford University Press. LeeKeenan, D., & Ponte, I. C. (2019). <i>From survive to thrive: A director's guide for leading an early childhood program</i>. National Association for the Education of Young Children. Washington, V., Gadson, B., & Amel, K. L. (2015). <i>The new early childhood professional: A step-by-step guide to overcoming Goliath</i>. Teachers College Press.

Evaluation	EduPASS Evaluation Tool for Early Childhood Educator Programmes					
Module structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 courses)</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Course 5.1: Fundamentals of Practical Teaching <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 4 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 2 h Seminar Teaching Units ○ 2 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours ● Course 5.2: Practical Strategies in ECE-Settings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 2 h Seminar Teaching Units ○ 4 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 2 h Self-Directed Working hours ● Course 5.3: Continuous Improvement and Evaluation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ 2 h Lecture Teaching Units ○ 4 h Workshop/Practical Teaching Units ○ 4 h Self-Directed Working hours 					
Learning outcomes <i>for Early Childhood Educators</i>	<p>The module will enable the Early Childhood Educator in training to build the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values) which serve as a foundation when engaging with the children they teach:</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="389 920 1402 1554"> <tr> <td data-bbox="389 920 890 1137"> Knowledge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pedagogical foundations ● Inclusive education principles ● Observation and documentation </td> <td data-bbox="890 920 1402 1137"> Skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Effective communication ● Activity design ● Conflict resolution ● Technology integration </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="389 1137 890 1554"> Attitudes: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging with children they teach:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Empathy ● Positive attitude ● Lifelong learning ● Reflective practice </td> <td data-bbox="890 1137 1402 1554"> Values: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging with children they teach:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inclusive, ethical practice ● Community engagement </td> </tr> </table>		Knowledge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Pedagogical foundations ● Inclusive education principles ● Observation and documentation 	Skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Effective communication ● Activity design ● Conflict resolution ● Technology integration 	Attitudes: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging with children they teach:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Empathy ● Positive attitude ● Lifelong learning ● Reflective practice 	Values: <i>ECEs in training will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging with children they teach:</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inclusive, ethical practice ● Community engagement
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Learning outcomes <i>for children/learners</i>	<p>The module will enable the Early Childhood Educator in training to support the children they teach to develop the following competencies (knowledge, skills, attitudes, values):</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="389 1666 1402 2069"> <tr> <td data-bbox="389 1666 890 1872"> Knowledge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Holistic development ● Inclusion and diversity </td> <td data-bbox="890 1666 1402 1872"> Skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communication, ● Problem-solving ● Collaboration ● Teamwork </td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="389 1872 890 2069"> Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i> </td> <td data-bbox="890 1872 1402 2069"> Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i> </td> </tr> </table>		Knowledge: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Holistic development ● Inclusion and diversity 	Skills: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Communication, ● Problem-solving ● Collaboration ● Teamwork 	Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i>	Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i>
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Attitudes: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following attitudes when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i>	Values: <i>Children will have engaged in activities that foster development of the following values when engaging in PAMPS activities with other children:</i>					

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empathy • Respect • Curiosity and motivation • Resilience and perseverance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inclusivity • Responsibility • Ethics and honesty
<p>Module Outcomes <i>action oriented outcomes and results for educators</i></p> <p><i>(based on Quality Statements from EU Framework for Early Childhood Education and Care, 2014)</i></p>	<p>The educator will have taken the first step towards being able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop practical pedagogical skills through interactive learning activities, fostering high-quality interactions with children. • Create inclusive learning environments that respect the diversity of children's backgrounds and needs. • Learn effective observation and documentation strategies to support individual and group needs. • Address group dynamics management and conflict resolution techniques, promoting a harmonious learning environment. • Adapt pedagogical practices to the individual and collective needs of children, ensuring a personalized learning experience. • Foster collaboration among educators, children, colleagues, and parents, strengthening trust and shared understanding within the educational community. • Receive immediate feedback on their practice, allowing them to integrate new techniques and strategies directly into their teaching. • promote a collaborative approach to the curriculum, where they reflect on their practice and develop new approaches based on evidence. 	
<p>Connection to other Core Module</p>	<p>Module 2: Principles of Teaching Children</p>	

Course Structure

Course Title	Fundamentals of Practical Teaching		
Course Number	5.1		
Course Description / Main Objective	Understand and implement key concepts of child development and inclusive education. Communicate effectively and manage classroom dynamics, fostering a collaborative environment.		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L	4 h	Teaching Unit 1: Introduction to Practical Teaching and Child Development
	W	2 h	Teaching Unit 2: Principles of Inclusive Education
	S	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Observation and Documentation techniques
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 4: Independent Learning and Practical Application
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Introduction to practical teaching in Early Childhood Education • Theories of child development and their application in the classroom • Case studies: Successful teaching practices 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Principles of inclusive education • Effective communication in practical teaching • Reflection and self-assessment of current pedagogical practices 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observation and documentation techniques • Simulations: Applying development theories in educational environments 	
	TU 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing personalized learning plans • Evaluating classroom strategies 	

Course Title	Practical Strategies in ECE-Settings		
Course Number	5.2		
Course Description / Main Objective	Design and execute developmentally appropriate activities, utilizing innovative teaching tools. Demonstrate empathy, respect, and a commitment to continuous learning and reflective practice.		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Designing Inclusive Educational Activities
	W	4 h	Teaching Unit 2: Managing Group Dynamics and Conflict Resolution
	S	2 h	Teaching Unit 3: Real-time Assessment and Feedback
	SDL	2 h	Teaching Unit 4: Self-Guided Skill Enhancement and Empathy in Practice
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Designing inclusive educational activities • Creating and testing educational materials • Developing an educational activity plan 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Managing group dynamics and conflict resolution • Role-playing: classroom conflict management • Practical exercises in observation and documentation 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Real-time assessment and feedback techniques • Practical exercises in observation and documentation 	
	TU 4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Applying tools independently • Personal development through Self-Assessment 	

Course Title	Continuous Improvement and Evaluation		
Course Number	5.3		
Course Description / Main Objective	Uphold high ethical standards, promoting inclusivity, and fostering strong connections with parents and the community		
Course Structure <i>(each module requires AT LEAST 2 Teaching Units)</i>	L	2 h	Teaching Unit 1: Continuous Improvement of Pedagogical Practices
	W / PE	4 h	Teaching Unit 2: Using Technology in Early Childhood Education
	SDL	4 h	Teaching Unit 3: Engaging Parents and the Community in the Educational Process
Course Content <i>(examples of specific Course Content based on EduPASS LTT workshops are shared as separate slide decks)</i>	TU 1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous improvement of pedagogical practices in early childhood education • Strategies for evaluating and improving pedagogical practices • Case studies: Successful teaching practices 	
	TU 2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Benefits and challenges of using technology in early childhood education • Useful technological tools for the early childhood classroom • Effective integration of technology into the educational curriculum 	
	TU 3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methods to actively involve parents in the educational process • Strategies to strengthen connections with the community • Examples of successful collaboration between the school, parents, and the community 	